

Irish Chemical Events

Lecture by Dr. Peter Morris (Science Museum, London) “*Form and Function: The History of the Chemistry Laboratory, 1700 to 2005*” and launch of the book “*Trinity College Dublin – 300 Years of Chemistry*”

Report by: John M. Kelly

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Trinity College Dublin

Event Type: Other

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<http://zenodo.org/communities/ice/>

Organising Committee: John Boland, Peter Boyle, David Grayson, John M. Kelly

Organisation: School of Chemistry, Trinity College Dublin

Event Sponsors

The Royal Society of Chemistry, Republic of Ireland Local Section

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A gift from the Dr. Mary Carson Benefaction, a friend of the School and one of the first female academics

Summary

On Monday, June 30th, we were delighted to launch a new book “*Trinity College Dublin – 300 years of Chemistry*”, written and edited by current and emeritus professors, John Boland, Peter Boyle, John Kelly, David Grayson and the late Brian McMurry (Figure 1). The book provides a fascinating history of the School and details its contributions to pharmaceutical and other industries as well as giving an insight into the stories of some of the distinguished people who have enriched our legacy. The launch event began with a seminar hosted by the Royal Society of Chemistry entitled “*Form and Function: The History of the Chemistry Laboratory, 1700-2005*”, which was given by Professor Peter Morris of the Science Museum in London (Figure 2). This was followed by the official launch of the book and a wine reception where school alumni as well as past and present staff were able to gather and share their memories and stories of their time with us.

Attendees

191 attendees registered on Eventbrite and it is estimated that an additional 20+ walk-ins attended the lecture and book launch (Figure 3).

The event was attended by current TCD Chemistry staff and students, including RSC and ICI members. Academics for other Schools and universities also attended, in addition to alumni and retired members of staff from the School of Chemistry. Several members from the School’s Industry Advisory Board were also in attendance, whose companies supported the launch.

The venue was fully wheelchair accessible, canapés provided gave diverse gluten-free and vegan options to cater for dietary requirements and a selection of non-alcoholic beverage options was available in addition to wine. EDI data was not collected at registration so exact gender split amongst the attendees is uncertain.

Target audience: academics, industrialists, undergraduates, postgraduates, alumni, general public, RSC members, ICI members.

Figure 1. Image of the jacket cover for the new book

Programme

5pm Lecture by Dr. Peter Morris - Form and Function: The History of the Chemistry Laboratory, 1700 to 2005.

6pm Official Launch of Book

6:15pm Wine and Canapé reception for attendees

The reception concluded at 8:30pm

Speaking about the book at the launch event, Prof. John Boland said:

"This book provides a historical perspective of the development of Chemistry at Trinity College Dublin, from its roots in medicine to how it became a fully-fledged independent discipline that ultimately led to the establishment in 1711 of one of the first departments of chemistry in Europe. In doing so it introduces the reader to the individuals who forged this history – teachers and researchers whose curiosity, passion and drive helped shape and secure the future of chemistry at Trinity for the generations that followed. It also lays bare the many challenges now facing Chemistry at Trinity in this era of multi-disciplinarity and record levels of participation in 3rd level education."

Feedback

Attendees provided exceptionally positive feedback during the event, both in terms of the timeliness of publication of a book on the School of Chemistry and the large numbers attending the event. Many attendees particularly welcomed the opportunity to meet old friends and colleagues. After the event, several attendees sent emails to the authors congratulating them on the book and the success of the launch.

The Book

100 books were sold at the event itself, following which the book became available at the Trinity bookstore and has since sold an additional 30 copies. The book is published by Hinds, 13 Carlisle Avenue, Dublin 4 and has ISBN 978-1-909442-09-2.

Figure 2. Professor Morris's opening lecture

Figure 3. Audience attending the opening lecture

A photo gallery is available at <https://chemistry.tcd.ie/news-events/gallery/BookLaunch.php>